

AUDITORS' INDEPENDENCE AND FINANCIAL REPORTING QUALITY OF LISTED DEPOSIT MONEY BANK IN NIGERIA.

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Abstract

The ultimate aim of audit is to ensure that all stakeholders have access to reliable and credible financial information, since the audit report adds credibility to financial statements which form the basis for economic and non-economic decisions made by shareholders and other stakeholders. Therefore, this study examined how auditors' independence determines the financial reporting quality of listed Deposit money banks in Nigeria. The study adopted an ex-post facto research design because secondary data were extracted from published annual reports of 15 listed Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria for a period of 10 years from year 2010 to 2019. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and inferential panel data analysis. Results from the data analysis showed that there is a significant positive relationship between Auditors' tenure and financial reporting quality. The provision of non-audit service had a negative relationship with financial reporting quality. The study also found an insignificant negative relationship between audit fees and financial reporting quality. It was also found that there is a positive relationship between audit firm size and financial reporting quality. The study, therefore, concluded that there is a significant relationship between the proxies to auditors' independence (auditors' tenure, non-audit services, audit fees, audit firm size) and financial reporting quality of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. The paper recommends that boards of directors of listed deposit money banks should encourage long audit tenure and discourage non-audit services because of the identified positive and negative impact of the two proxies, respectively, on the financial reporting quality of listed Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria.

Keywords: Audit tenure, non-audit services, audit fees, financial reporting quality.

1.0 Introduction

The value and credibility of financial reports have been issues of concern among shareholders, researchers, regulatory organizations and the Accounting profession as a whole, since financial report is the primary medium for conveying information to stakeholders who make use of the information for taking informed economic decisions (Hassan & Bello, 2013). As a result, regulatory bodies made various pronouncements and introduced supervisory mechanisms such as corporate governance structures to protect the interest of owners and stakeholders of organizations.

Despite the fact that the banking sector is one of the most supervised industries in Nigeria and all over the world, the sector has recorded high incidences of bank distress, money laundering, mismanagement and persistent bank failures over the past decades. This has heightened questions on the adequacy of auditing and corporate governance practices. For instance, the

financial industry malpractices accounts for up to 50% of the recorded fraud cases in Nigeria and these fraud cases have similar contextual issue of concealing huge non-performing loans. It was discovered that the managing director of Oceanic bank approved a huge sum of N747 billion loans to family members (Okaro, 2015). Another bank fraud case in Nigeria is that of Skye bank where the chairman of the bank owed the bank a sum of N102 billion for many years (Akintoye, 2019; Okaro, Okafor, & Ofoegbu, 2013). Also, the Nigerian banking industry lost N19.77 billion in the first 6 months of 2018 to fraud cases (Aderemi, 2018).

In reference to the aforementioned banking distress, a lot of attention has been drawn to the part played by accountants and auditors of those distressed banks, because these auditors certified the going concern status of these banks prior to their collapse. The public expectation is that, auditors are expected to report any form of financial misconduct when issuing their report to the shareholders in order to strengthen the credibility and transparency of financial reports as well as formulating strategies that can detect any type of fraud (Ehiwario, 2016; Adeyemi, 2011).

However, prior studies and current body of literature suggest that auditors have notoriously misused their expertise to enshroud and conceal white collar crimes. For instance, Akintola Williams Deloitte was accused of aiding the misrepresentation of the accounts of Afribank plc and for purposefully inflating the turnover of Cadbury Nigeria PLC. Similarly, the Nigerian banking industry lost up to 6 billion naira to fraud between the year 1990 to 1994 (Bakre, 2007; Miko & Hassan, 2010).

Thus, regulatory bodies, prior empirical literatures attributed bank distress, corporate failure, earnings management to the impairment of auditors' independence (Lauwo & Olatunde, 2010). Consequently, long audit-client tenure has emerged as one of the most debated threats to auditors' independence based on prior studies due to familiarity threat which reduces the professional scepticism of the auditor, thereby leading to audit failure. Hence, the Sarbanes Oxley Act of 2002 validated this perspective as it mandates the replacement of the audit partners leading the audit team of audit engagements for every 5 years (Eyenubo, Mohammed & Ali, 2017).

In addition to the issue of audit tenure, Fees paid for management advisory services, is another factor that the accounting world has also raised concerns about. It has been perceived that provision of non-audit service can lead to self-interest threat to auditors' independence. Most prior studies on auditors' independence posits that, a higher audit fees can make an auditor to be economically dependent on the client, which is referred to as the economic bond theory (Trainor, 2009; Bhuiyan, Rahman & Sultana, 2020).

Having considered audit fees, auditors' tenure and non-audit services as threats to auditors' independence, other researchers in prior studies affirm that the size of the audit firm could also be a major determining factor of auditors' independence (Comprix & Huang, 2015; Kamolsakulchai, 2015; DeFond, Erkens & Zhang, 2016). The argument is that, small audit firms or the non-big 4 firms could impair their independence in a bid to keep audit clients and the corresponding incomes from such clients (Lennox & Pittman, 2010). On the contrary, Cadbury Nigeria was audited by one of the big 4s, yet the independence of their auditors was impaired.

Hence, the notion of small firms compromising their independence as result of their size has been refuted by empirical studies (Mikko & Hassa, 2010).

This suggests that most corporate scandal could have been avoided if Accountants and Auditors have complied with stipulated ethical rules and conduct expected of them (Altamuro & Beatty, 2010). The International Accounting Standard Board (IASB) published an exposure draft in 2018 on qualitative characteristics of an ideal financial report which are understandability, faithful presentation, comparability, verifiability and timeliness. According to the conceptual framework, the principal requirements needed to have a quality financial report is by complying strictly with the qualitative characteristics stipulated by IASB. Olagunju (2011) posits that auditors' independence influences the quality and reliability of financial reports.

In view of the above, it can be established that auditors' independence has a critical role in ensuring that companies, especially listed companies, produce quality financial report in order to increase investors' and other shareholders' confidence as well as encourage potential investors. Hence, the main objective of this study is to investigate the nexus between auditors' independence and financial reporting quality of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria.

2.0 Literature review

Conceptual review

Maury (2000) defined an auditor's independence as the attribute and quality of being free from control, undue pressure and dominance of the third party. Similarly, Olagunju (2011) referred auditors' independence to as measures taken by the auditors to steer clear from circumstances and individuals that can influence their professional behaviour or judgements. Aderibigbe (2005), auditors' independence in two different ways, the first definition defined independence as the absence of a personal relationship between the auditors and the auditee, while the second definition connotes freedom in executing the duties, rights and power of the auditor.

Therefore, auditors' independence safeguards objectivity and enforces confidence and assuredness in the end-users of financial statements (Alaraji, Al-Dulaimi, Sabri & Ion, 2017). In addition, Auditor's independence can be illustrated in three ways which are, programming, investigative and reporting independence. Programming independence enables the auditors to select the best audit approach in the course of the audit assignment and this implies that auditors must discharge their duties freely without any prejudice (Akther & Xu, 2020; Alaraji, Al-Dulaimi, Sabri & Ion, 2017).

Determinants of auditors' independence

The determinants or proxies of auditors' independence in this study are, non-audit services, audit tenure, audit fees and audit firm size..

Non-audit services (NAS)

The notion of whether an auditor should perform both auditing and non-auditing services to the same client has been a global controversial issue and the debate is ongoing. Tax computation and

assessment, management information system, liquidation and receivership, financial advice, company registration and final accounts preparation are all examples of non-audit services and these services have been considered as a prospective threat to auditors' independence when rendered together with audit assignments to the same client (Lim & Tan, 2008). Wu and Ying (2016) defined Non-audit services as all services provided by an auditor that is not regarded as an audit, which implies that NAS is referred to as those services that do not require forming an opinion on the truth and fair view on the financial statements of the client.

Audit tenure

Audit tenure can be defined as the length of time an audit firm or the time frame an engagement partner has consistently audited the client's company (Johnson, Khurana & Reynolds, 2002; Geiger & Raghunandan 2002). Audit tenure refers to the period in which an external auditor audits the financial report of its audit client. There have conflicting views or standpoints from extant studies as regards the appropriate length of auditor tenure with audit clients. For instance, the first school of thought holds the view that auditors gain more expertise if the audit tenure is longer and therefore their ability to identify misstatements and fraud (Carey & Simnett 2006; Bratten, Causholli & Omer, 2019).

Audit fees

Audit fees can be described as the amount paid by the audit client to the auditor for the audit of the organizations financial report on behalf of the shareholders (El-Gammal, 2012). Al-khaddash, Nawas and Ramadan (2013) define audit fees as all expenses paid by the auditee for statutory audit, including fees incurred on non-audit services.

CAMA (2004) mandated all quoted companies in Nigeria to employ the services of an external auditor. Thus, the apparent responsibility of this stipulation is for the statutory auditor to express his unbiased opinion on the financial reports of the Auditee and by so doing the external auditor is entitled to a certain fee which is usually discretionary (Aliu, Okpanachi & Mohammed, 2018).

2.1.5 Audit firm size

Asides other factors suggested by prior studies on threats to the independence of auditors, audit firm size has also been considered as a the key indicators of Auditors' independence and the main concern raised in this regard is whether audit judgements of auditors from large audit firms varies or supersedes that of medium sized or small audit firms and as a result, there are conflicting views accompanied with opposing results.

Audit firm size has been classified by many studies using different thresholds. The most popular benchmark for the classification of audit firms is usually predicated on the number of audit clients an audit firm possesses and it ranges from 30 – 70 clients (small); 70-120 clients (medium) and 120 clients and above (Comprix & Huang, 2015; Defond & Lennox, 2011). Other studies classified audit firms as local, regional and international, while the most common

classification by many studies is Big 4 and non-big four (Lawrence, Minutti-Meza & Zhang, 2011).

Financial reporting quality

Financial reporting entails the publishing of financial and non-financial information to all stakeholders regarding the financial performance and financial status of the organization over a particular time frame, needed to make economic decisions and assessing the performance of the management (Enofe, Aronwam&Abadua, 2013). These stakeholders include – potential shareholders, suppliers, members of the public and the government. The frequency of financial information publication for listed companies is quarterly and yearly.

Financial reporting is generally referred to as the final product of accounting information and the normal parts of financial reports are statement of financial position, income statement, statement of cash flows and information on the ownership structure, additional information and analysis (Gaynor, Kelton, Mercer & Yohn, 2016).

Qualitative characteristics of accounting information

The qualitative attributes of accounting information can be divided into two main parts and they are fundamental (which is compulsory) and enhancing (which implies good to have).

Fundamental or Primary qualitative attributes of financial information serves as the basis for the usefulness of accounting information which are *relevance and faithful representation* while enhancing or secondary qualitative attributes of financial information that indicates how valuable the information is and they are; “*verifiability, timeliness, understandability and comparability*”(Renkas, Goncharenko, &Lukianets, 2015).

Underpinning theory

Stakeholder’s theory

Corporate organizations have been regarded as one of the most powerful and exceptional establishments on earth with different support groups that rely on their success or going concern. These support groups are regarded as stakeholders and these stakeholders mainly include the shareholders of the organization, who are responsible for the funding of the organization and other stakeholders like, employees, government, suppliers, competitors, banks and other financial institutions who offer services that sustains the organization one way or the other.

Hence, stakeholder’s theory proposed by Edward Freeman in 1984 posits that an organization’s stakeholder includes a person or any group of people connected to the organization or affected by its activities. Hence, organization should be answerable to all groups of people connected to its organization and not the shareholders of the company alone. This notion is opposed to the traditional theory proposed by Milton Friedman, which affirms that, business organizations should only be concerned about the shareholders of a company.

Therefore, the stakeholder's theory underpins this study, because the whole essence of auditing an organization is to verify the credibility of financial reports used by shareholders and other stakeholders for economic and non-economic decision making.

Empirical review

Prior to the Enron scandal, most literatures on auditors independence were more on audit fees, low balling, Non-Audit service, Audit committee independence etc. preceding the year 1981, researchers allege that the firm size does not affect the Audit Quality but a study done by De Angelo (1981) countered this view with the notion that large audit firms have more to lose by failing to report a discovered breach in a particular client's record, Whereas, small and medium firms have less clients to loose. In support of Deangelo's study, Gul (1989) examined the effects of audit committee, client financial condition, and audit firms' size on New Zealand Bankers' perceptions of auditors' independence using ANOVA and the results from the study suggest that firms providing MAS as a separate division in the audit firm are perceived as a lower risk of losing independence. While, small audit firms were perceived to be more at risk of losing independence than large audit firms.

So also, another study done by De Angelo (1981) investigated the relationship between lowballing and Auditors' independence and the impact of disclosure regulation using modelling. According to the result from the study lowballing does not impair auditors' independence, which was in contrary to allegations made by the Securities and Exchange Commission on audit fees and auditors' independence.

A cross-cultural study on perceived Auditors' independence and cultural differences across United Kingdom, India and Malaysia was done by Patel and Saros (2000). The authors investigated the perception of final year undergraduate students in Accounting and recommended that a global set of audit procedures and codes of professional conduct is needed in order to resolve cross-cultural differences. With the introduction of IFRS and ISA most countries of the world have been able to cross that bay of cultural differences.

Literatures and researches during the pre-Enron era were more on factors like Audit committee (AC), board size and board independence for instance, Klein (2002) did a study on Economic determinants of Audit Committee Independence and found out that audit committee independence increases with board size and board independence. An effective audit committee with qualified members will strengthen the activities Auditors. One of the essential attribute on an effective audit committee is diligence. Asides diligence, other factors that affects the effectiveness of the audit committee as identified byDeZoort, Hermanson, Archambeault and Reed (2002) includes audit committee composition, authority and resources.

One of the biggest scandals in the 1990s before Enron was that of a waste management corporation based in Houston, a publicly traded company. The management of the company reported 1.7 billion dollars as fake earnings even with their accounts being audited by Arthur

Anderson. The company and their Auditors were penalized. Most of the scandals during the 1990s were attributed to poor audit quality and ineffective audit committee. For instance, Carcello & Neal (2000) examined the relationship between the composition of financially distressed audit firms' audit committee and the likelihood of receiving going concern reports. Their findings indicated that there's a correlation between higher percentage of affiliated director in an audit team and the lower probability that the Auditor will issue a going concern report. The Enron case triggered lots of reactions from the regulatory bodies like International Organization of Securities Commissions to issue a statement in October, 2002 on principles of auditors' independence and corporate governance with the main objective of overseeing the quality and credibility of an Organization's financial reporting.

The post-Enron scandal overturned the tune and the focus of research on auditing entirely and the post Enron era is from year 2002 till date. Thus, most studies after the Enron scandal were ultimately on the psychological factors of the auditor, cultural differences, emotional intelligence of the auditor, the quality of audit and the independence of the Auditors by examining those factors that can impair the auditors' independence because once the independence of the auditor is eroded, the audit quality will be substandard and invariably, the financial reports will become unreliable. In addition, most studies used audit quality as a proxy for financial reporting quality (DeFond, Erkens & Zhang, 2016). Hence, this study will focus on factors like audit tenure, non-audit services, audit fees and firm size.

Firstly, audit tenure refers to the period in which an external auditor audits the financial report of its audit client. There have been conflicting views or standpoints from extant studies as regards the appropriate length of auditor tenure with audit clients. For instance, the first school of thought holds the view that auditors gain more expertise if the audit tenure is longer and therefore their ability to identify misstatements and fraud (Carey & Simnett 2006; Bratten, Causholli & Omer, 2019).

Bratten, Causholli and Omer (2019) investigated the relationship between audit tenure, bank complexity and financial reporting quality, the result of the study reveals that there is a positive relationship between long audit tenure and Financial Reporting Quality which is necessary due to the complexity of the banking industry. The study suggests that that a short audit tenure can reduce Financial Reporting Quality.

On the other hand, the other school of thought holds the view that long audit tenure results in an undue relationship which can consequently lead to a reduction in the financial reporting quality. For example, Ikhara (2015) suggests that long audit tenure will affect the financial reporting quality. Eyenubo, Mohamed and Ali (2017) examined the relationship between audit tenure and audit quality, the result from the study show that long audit tenure affects audit quality.

Secondly, the issue of Auditors providing non-audit services (NAS) to the audit client is still seriously debated amongst researchers. The main concern arising out of the debate is based on how provision of NAS to the same audit client can affect auditor's independence, therefore

affecting audit quality and invariably affecting financial reporting quality. Keeping in mind the whole essence of auditing is to ensure that users of financial reports can make informed decisions based on the audited financial report.

Therefore, the credibility of such assurance depends on the independence, both in fact and in appearance, of the auditor. Over the years, however, the independence of auditors has come under increased scrutiny because of their joint provision of both audit and non-audit services.

Although, the issue of NAS has been overly studied but there is a scarce number of empirical studies that addressed the impact of NAS on financial reporting quality. Nevertheless, there are some papers on NAS and FRQ such as, Koh, Rajgopal and Srinivasan (2012) who examined the relationship between NAS and FRQ specifically during the years 1978 to 1980 for a sample made up of S&P firms to verify whether high NAS fees in relation to audit fees are associated with poor quality of financial reporting. To a greater extent, the authors discovered that the provision of NAS is associated with an improvement in earnings quality that is a lower likelihood of reporting a small earnings surprise and an increase in earning in-formativeness.

Also Habib (2012) considered the net effect of non audit services on financial reporting quality using meta analysis to aggregate and correct statistical results of related prior studies to provide a much reliable precision with respect to the findings. The meta analysis results show that investors adjudged non audit service as a threat to financial reporting quality.

Huang, Mishra and Raghunandan (2007) used prior data from 6,891 SEC filings in 2003 and 2004. The results from the study indicate that, auditors were more objective in the post-SOX era and found that higher value of non-audit services fee lowers biased financial reporting quality.

Thirdly, there have been lots of controversies regarding the impact of audit firm size on audit quality and auditors independence. Some studies suggest that the size of an audit firm indicates its level of audit quality, that is, a large audit firm implies a higher audit quality, while a small audit firm portrays a lower audit quality (Jerry & Saidu, 2018; Kamolsakulchai, 2015; Lennox & Pittman, 2010).

However, some studies suggest that there is no difference between the audit quality of a big 4 and non-big 4 and what accounts for the difference in the audit quality of the two is client characteristics which includes; a sound corporate governance, good internal control system, high asset turnover, good management and ability to pay a high audit fee (Lawrence *et al*, 2011; Comprix & Huang, 2015)

Lastly, Mohammed, Joshua and Ahmed (2018) examined the relationship between audit fees and audit quality using secondary data extracted from nine companies engaged in the downstream sector of the petroleum industry, the findings from the study indicates that there is a negative

relationship between audit fees and audit quality and as a matter of fact, the study asserts that a higher audit fees can impair auditors’ independence and invariably results into a lower audit quality. On the contrary, Rahmina and Agoes (2014) studied the effect of audit fees on auditors’ independence and audit quality. The study operationalized audit fees using the size of the auditee, auditee’s accounting system complexity and audit risk as a measure of audit fees using primary data. The result from the study indicates that audit fees significantly influences audit quality.

3.0 Methodology

The research design for this study is *Ex-post facto* research design which relies on the use of past data to predict current behavior of the variables considered for this study. The population of this study is listed Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria, which are 17 in total. However, 15 Deposit “Money Banks were used for this study due to the availability of data and they are, Zenith bank, Access bank, first bank, FCMB, Fidelity bank, Guaranty trust bank, sterling bank, Unity bank, union bank and Wema bank. The data was analyzed using multiple regression analysis”.

Model specification:

$$FRQ = \beta_0 + \beta_1 AT_{i,t} + \beta_2 NAS_{i,t} + \beta_3 AF_{i,t} + \beta_4 AFS_{i,t} + \varepsilon$$

Variable	Type of variable	Measurement	Notation
Financial reporting quality	Dependent	Fundamental and enhancing qualitative characteristics indexed checklist	FRQ
Auditor’s tenure	Independent	The number of years an auditor has been with the client.	AT
Non-audit services	Independent	The natural log of non-audit fees	NAS
Audit fees	Independent	The natural log of audit fees.	AF
Audit firm size	Independent	The total number of employees in an audit firm.	AFS

4.0 Data Analysis and Interpretation

Panel data were collected from 15 for ten years each. The annual reports of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria were collected to carry out this research; banks were chosen for this study because of the sense of reliability and extent of widespread acceptability by stakeholders (Haniffa and Cooke, 2005; Deegan and Rankin, 1997).

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistics analysis of the dependent variable (financial reporting quality) and the independent variables (auditors’ independence; Non-Audit Service, Audit Fees, Audit Firm Size, and Auditor’s Tenure) were presented in Table 4.1. Descriptive statistics like Standard deviation, Skewness, Mean, Kurtosis, Maximum, and Minimum of each variable were presented to show the measures of variances, measures of central tendency, and measures of the model’s normality.

Data distribution with high kurtosis or a highly skewed nature indicates non-normality, which has random effects on estimation or specification (Hall & Wang, 2005).

Table 4.1: Descriptive of the effect of auditors' independence on financial reporting quality.

	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max	Skewness	Kurtosis
FRQ	150	65.33333	15.92913	0	93	0.0000	0.0000
AT	150	4.906667	2.913396	0	10	0.4510	0.0000
NAS	150	1.890158	3.269818	0	8.22908	0.0000	0.0454
					8.96567		0.0000
AF	150	8.070794	1.394514	0	2	0.0000	
					5.49415		0.4783
AFS	150	4.278548	1.941792	0	9	0.0000	

Table 4.1 revealed that the average value of financial reporting quality of the Nigerian commercial banks is 65.33333, 15.92913 is the standard deviation which implies that on the two sides of the mean of FRQ, the data deviate from the mean by 15.92913. The maximum value of FRQ, as well as the minimum of FRQ, are 93 and 0, respectively, and these indicate a positive performance of Nigerian commercial banks. 0.0000 is the coefficient of Skewness of FRQ, which indicates that the FRQ has a normal distribution. The kurtosis value of FRQ as reported is 0.0000, which implies FRQ is neither low nor high; it is mesokurtic, which means that FRQ has a normal distribution.

Table 4.1 further reveals that auditor's tenure has an aggregate mean of 4.906667, 2.913396 is the standard deviation which implies that on the two sides of the mean of AT, the data deviate from the mean by 2.913396, and the maximum, as well as the minimum of AT, is 10 and 0, respectively which indicates that some auditors did not spend up to a year in office while some spend as much as ten years as an auditor in their banks. 0.4510 is the coefficient of Skewness of AT, which indicates that the AT is skewed right. The kurtosis value of AT as reported is 0.0000, which implies AT is neither low nor high; this means that AT has a normal distribution.

Also, the mean value of non-audit service is 1.890158, 3.269818 is the standard deviation which implies that on the two sides of the mean of NAS, the data deviate from the mean by 3.269818, and the maximum, as well as the minimum of NAS is 8.22908 and 0, respectively. 0.0000 is the coefficient of Skewness of NAS, which indicates that the NAS has a normal distribution. The kurtosis value of NAS as reported is 0.0454, which implies NAS is close to zero; this implies that NAS has a normal distribution.

It was also revealed from Table 4.1 that the average value of audit fees of the Nigerian commercial banks is 8.070794, 1.394514 is the standard deviation which implies that on the two sides of the mean of AF, the data deviate from the mean by 1.394514, and the maximum, as well as the minimum of AF, are 8.965672 and 0, respectively. 0.0000 is the coefficient of Skewness of AF, which indicates that the AF has a normal distribution. The kurtosis value of AF as reported is

0.0000, which implies AF is neither low nor high; it is mesokurtic, which implies that AF has a normal distribution.

Finally, Audit Firm Size has an estimated mean value of 4.278548, 1.941792 is the standard deviation which implies that on the two sides of the mean of AFS, the data deviate from the mean by 1.941792, and the maximum, as well as the minimum of AFS, is 5.494159 and 0, respectively. 0.0000 is the coefficient of Skewness of AFS, which indicates that the AFS has a normal distribution. As reported, the kurtosis value of AFS is 0.4783, which implies AFS is neither low nor high; this implies that AFS has lighter tails than a normal distribution.

4.2 Correlation Matrix

The correlation analysis, according to Pallant (2011), is very important in showing the strength and direction of the undeviating association among the variables of the study. It was proposed by Joseph (2010) that when there is no relationship, the correlation value will be 0, while an excellent relationship is when the correlation value is +/-1.0. This is consistent with the submission of Hair, Tatham, Anderson, Babin, and Black (2010), who also posited that to be sure that the study is free from multicollinearity problem, the value of the correlation matrix be below 0.70. In measuring the strength of the relationship of all the variables of this study, this study adopts the Pearson Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation. Table 4.2 is the summary of the results of the Pearson correlation Coefficients of FRQ, AT, NAS, AF, and AFS.

Table 4.2: Pearson Correlation Matrix

	FRQ	AT	NAS	AF	AFS
FRQ	1.0000				
AT	0.3440*	1.0000			
NAS	0.2394*	0.5004*	1.0000		
AF	0.7037*	0.3655*	0.1980	1.0000	
AFS	0.1696	0.3916*	0.3226*	0.4748*	1.0000
	0.0380	0.0000	0.0001	0.0000	

Source: *Stata Output, 2021.*

The correlation analysis in Table 4.2 shows that the relationship between financial reporting quality and auditor’s tenure is 0.3440. At 0.01 level (2-tailed), the relationship between financial reporting quality and auditor’s tenure is statistically significant. The relationship between financial reporting quality and non-audit service is 0.2394. At 0.01 level (2-tailed), the relationship between financial reporting quality and non-audit service is statistically significant.

The correlation analysis in Table 4.2 shows that the relationship between financial reporting quality and audit fees is 0.7037. At 0.01 level (2-tailed), the relationship between financial reporting quality and audit fees is statistically significant. Thus, other auditors’ independence

variables aside from audit fees account for variations or changes in financial reporting quality by 50.48%. The relationship between financial reporting quality and audit firm size is 0.1696. At 0.01 level (2-tailed), the relationship between financial reporting quality and audit firm size is statistically significant. Thus, other auditors' independence variables aside from audit firm size account for variations or changes in financial reporting quality by 97.12%.

4.3 Regression Assumptions Tests

To conduct the panel analysis effectively, econometric analysis is used. This study used one equation to accomplish the objective of this research, which is to examine the effect of auditors' independence on financial reporting quality using multiple regression analysis. The model was estimated with Panel Data Regression and thus conducted robustness tests. Hausman test was conducted to choose either to use random or fixed model.

4.3.1 Multicollinearity and Heteroscedasticity Test

The Tolerance Value and Variance Inflation Factor were used to conduct the Multicollinearity test, and the effects of Heteroskedasticity and Autocorrelation were tested using Cook-Weisberg/Breuch, and Pagan test and Table 4.3.1 is the summary of the results.

Variable	Multicollinearity Test		Homoscedasticity Test
	Variable Inflation Factors	Tolerance	Hottest, Breusch-Pagan Financial Reporting Quality
AT	1.52	0.656980	chi2(1) = 4.62
AFS	1.43	0.700159	Prob > chi2 = 0.0317
NAS	1.37	0.729032	
AF	1.36	0.734829	
Mean VIF	1.42		

*The p-value for financial reporting quality is insignificant, this implies homoscedasticity in the variance of these residuals.

The test for heteroskedasticity performed with the Breuch Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test shows chi2(1) of 4.62 with a p-value of 0.0317. This implies that the assumption of homoscedasticity (constant variance of the error term) is satisfied, implying that with respect to the model of this study, OLS estimators is appropriate. The absence of the perfect multicollinearity is shown among the explanatory variables as revealed in Table 4.3, this is indicated by the mean VIF, which is 1.42. This is based on the decision criterion of VIF, which is, there is perfect multicollinearity when the VIF value is 10 or above 10. The results of collinearity tested with Tolerance is consistent with the results of VIF, which revealed that the independent variables (Auditor's Tenure = 0.656980, Audit Firm Size = 0.700159, Non-Audit Service = 0.729032, and Audit Fees = 0.734829) all have Tolerance values less than 1. This further shows that there are no collinearity problems. These diagnostic tests show no such severity.

4.3.2 The Hausman Test

To determine whether the fixed effect model or random effect model is appropriate, this part of the paper the Hausman test conduct.

Test Summary	Chi-Square	Prob>chi ²
Hausman Test	0.02	0.8772

Table 4.4: Examine the appropriate regression model for the analysis

As reported in Table 4.4, the P-value (0.8772) is observed to be greater than the 5% significance level, so the alternative is rejected while the null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, the Hausman Test concluded that the random effect model is the appropriate test for this study.

4.3.3 The effect of auditors’ independence on financial reporting quality

Table 4.5: Summary of Regression Analysis

FRQ	Coef.	Std. Err.	Z	P> z	[95% Conf. Interval]
AT	1.074415	.4563156	2.35	0.019	.1800523 1.968777
NAS	-1.39e-08	3.07e-08	-0.45	0.651	-7.42e-08 4.64e-08
AF	-1.74e-09	8.23e-09	-0.21	0.833	-1.79e-08 1.44e-08
AFS	0.0000197	.0000169	1.16	0.244	-.0000134 .0000528
Cons	57.61585	3.386354	17.01	0.000	50.97872 64.25298
Rho	.56385132	Prob > chi2	0.0001	sigma_	10.337553
				u	
Wald chi2(4)	23.68	corr(u_i, X)	0	sigma_e	9.0918596
			(assumed)		

Source: *Stata Output, 2021.*

The summary of the regression model is presented in Table 4.5. The model of the relationship between auditors’ independence (Non-Audit Service, Audit Fees, Audit Firm Size, and Auditor’s Tenure) and financial reporting quality is summarized in Table 4.5. The causal relationship between AT, NAS, AF, AFS and FRQ in the sample was suggested by the random effects panel data estimation, and it shows that the relationship is influenced by cross-section specific effects, which are realizations of independent random variables with finite variance, mean zero, and uncorrelated with the idiosyncratic residuals.

As presented in Table 4.5, 0.5639 of the variance, as depicted by the Rho value, is due to differences across panels which implies that non-audit service, audit fees, auditor’s tenure, and audit firm size explain changes in financial reporting quality by 56.29%, it shows that 56.39%, it shows that 56.29% of the systematic variation of the financial reporting quality is accounted for by auditors’ independence, thus, other auditors’ independence variables not included in this study account for variations or changes in financial reporting quality by 43.71%.

In testing the model’s reliability, Table 4.5 reveals 0.0001 as the significance value of the effect of auditors’ independence on financial reporting quality, which is smaller when compared with

the critical value (95% significance level). The model, therefore, is statistically significant in predicting the relationship that exists between auditors' independence and financial reporting quality.

Considering the effect of each of the variables on financial reporting quality, it was revealed from Table 4.4 that Auditor's Tenure (AT) has a positive and significant effect on the financial reporting quality of listed Deposit Money bank in Nigeria, with the Z-value of 2.35 from the coefficient of 1.074415 which is statistically significant at P-value of 0.05 (5% level of significance).

Table 4.5 also indicates that Non-Audit Service (NAS) has no significant effect on the financial reporting quality of listed Deposit Money bank in Nigeria, with a Z-value of -0.45, from the coefficient of 0.0212, which is not statistically significant at a p-value of 0.651 (0.05 levels of significance). This result suggests that non-audit service has a negative effect on the financial reporting quality of listed Deposit Money banks in Nigeria; however, at a 5% significance level, it is not statistically significant.

Table 4.5 shows that Audit Fees (AF) does not have a significant effect on the financial reporting quality of listed Deposit Money bank in Nigeria and the relationship between financial reporting quality and audit fees with a Z-value of -0.21, from the coefficient of -1.74e-09, which implies that audit fees is not statistically significant at a p-value of 0.833 (5% level of significance).

The z-value of audit firm size is 1.16 with a P-value of 0.244 and a coefficient value of 0.0000197. Comparing the P-value (0.244) with 0.05 shows that audit firm size has a positive effect that is not significant to the financial reporting quality.

Conclusion and recommendations

The analysis above shows that auditors' independence is a major determinant of financial reporting quality in Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria, since the rho value of the effect of auditors' independence on financial reporting quality is 0.5629, which connotes that the proxies for auditors' independence (audit tenure, non-audit services, audit fees and audit firm size) can explain 56% of variation in financial reporting quality and the implication of this from the perspective of stakeholders is that uncompromised auditors independence will improve the quality of financial reports and that auditors should act in the best interest of stakeholders by avoiding circumstances that can jeopardize their independence. For instance, the provision of non-audit services to the same audit client can impair auditors' independence based on the result from this study.

Additionally, long audit tenure should be encouraged because the results from the analysis suggests that long audit tenure improves the quality of financial reports in the Nigerian Deposit Money Banks but the threshold of ten years stipulated by the Central Bank of Nigeria should be enforced and this study's result in this regard aligns with the study done by Bratten *et al*, (2019).

Furthermore, the findings from the analysis also show that high audit fees charged by audit firms in Nigeria can affect their independence and can reduce the quality of financial reporting. Aliu *et al* (2018) study on auditors' independence, affirms the result of this study. Therefore, regulators should pay attention to audit fees structures to forestall the likely future impairment of auditors' independence.

In conclusion, the result from the analysis also indicates that there is a significant positive relationship between audit firm size and financial reporting quality. This implies that, the financial reporting quality of an audit firm is largely dependent on the size of the audit firm. The result Jerry and Saidu (2018) attest to the fact that, the bigger the size of an audit firm, the higher the financial reporting quality of their clients.

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